

MECHANISMS FOR INTENSIFYING STUDENTS' THINKING ACTIVITIES BASED ON HISTORICAL EXPERIMENTS

I.Menlimuratova

Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xojaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti mustaqil izlanuvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15243368>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the mechanisms for developing students' thinking activity using historical experiences. The current role and new challenges of the digital transformation process in the present education system are also discussed.*

Keywords: *Historical experiences, Modern school, tool, education system, active and independent thinking, ability, skill, case study.*

Introduction. The current processes of globalization and digital transformation are posing new challenges for the education system. Modern schools and universities should not limit themselves to merely conveying information, but should also ensure the development of students' critical and creative thinking abilities. In this context, utilizing historical experiences serves as a crucial tool, as history is not merely about memorizing past events, but also the art of understanding cause-and-effect relationships, making conclusions, analyzing, and defining direction for the future.

Today, the education system is focused on developing students' active and independent thinking skills. In this process, historical experiences play a crucial role, as they can serve as a foundation for developing effective mechanisms to accelerate cognitive activities. Analyzing historical events, studying the decisions of historical figures, and drawing conclusions from past experiences - all of these contribute to developing critical and creative thinking skills in students. History is not only a collection of facts, but also a science that requires thinking and analysis. For example, analyzing the decisions of great statesmen and the directions of development of historical processes teaches students strategic thinking. In addition, studying historical events from various points of view develops multifaceted and deep thinking.

One of the most important tasks facing the education system in the 21st century is teaching students to think independently, critically, and creatively. In the process of acquiring modern knowledge, merely obtaining factual information is not sufficient. It is crucial to analyze this knowledge, examine it from various perspectives, form one's own stance, and find solutions to problems. In this case, the use of historical experience is a very effective tool, helping to develop students' skills in logical thinking, reasoning, and strategic decision-making.

Objective: To identify mechanisms for developing critical and creative thinking in students by using historical experience and evaluating their effectiveness.

Based on historical experience, developing mechanisms for accelerating students' thinking and analyzing their significance in the educational process. For this purpose, the following tasks have been defined:

1. Studying the relationship between historical experiences and cognitive activities.
2. Study and evaluate methodological approaches to developing thinking, and assess the effectiveness of historical approaches in the learning process.

3. Develop methods for utilizing historical case studies in the educational process and propose practical approaches for implementing these mechanisms.
4. Develop decision-making skills through the analysis of historical events.
5. Identify mechanisms for developing thinking through historical methods and develop recommendations for the practical application of historical methods.

Historical knowledge expands a person's thinking capacity, develops critical analysis skills, and enhances understanding of cause-and-effect relationships. In the process of studying historical experiences, students acquire the following important abilities:

A comprehensive approach to problems - comparing and analyzing various historical sources.

Decision-making skills - the study of the decisions of historical figures and their consequences.

Decision-making skills - the study of the decisions of historical figures and their consequences.

Logical analysis involves understanding cause-and-effect relationships and comparing historical periods.

There are several important aspects to utilizing historical experiences:

1. Developing critical thinking - students compare various historical sources and evaluate their reliability.

2. Increasing creative thinking - creates the opportunity to develop new ideas based on historical events.

3. Developing problem-solving skills - students learn to find solutions by discussing historical problems.

To make effective use of historical experiences, the following mechanisms are recommended:

1. Analysis of problematic situations.

Students are given various historical situations and are required to make independent decisions.

For example: “If you were Amir Temur, what decision would you have made?” through such questions they are taught to analyze.

2. Method of historical case study.

Reviewing certain historical events as cases and drawing conclusions from them. For example, studying the decisions of leaders during World War II.

3. Historical disputes and debates.

By defending the positions of various historical figures, students develop communication and argumentation skills.

4. Comparative analysis of historical experiences in relation to contemporary issues.

Students compare historical events with current events, identifying similarities and differences. The decisions of great philosophers, statesmen, and scientists, as well as the processes that occurred in the past, allow us to draw important conclusions for the development of society. Historical knowledge helps develop a person's thinking abilities in the following directions:

Critical thinking involves analyzing historical events and understanding their causes and consequences.

Logical thinking is understanding the variability of historical processes and studying cause-and-effect relationships.

Creative thinking is approaching historical problems in a new way and offering alternative solutions.

Decision-making skills - analysis of decisions made by historical figures and their results.

Conclusions and recommendations: Applying historical experiences in the educational process helps develop critical, creative, and logical thinking in students. Mechanisms such as analyzing problematic situations, conducting historical debates, and utilizing the case study method are considered effective for intensifying thinking activities. Therefore, it is important to make extensive use of historical experience in the educational process.

Historical experiences serve as a valuable resource for accelerating students' thinking activities. By analyzing historical processes, they develop critical, creative, and logical thinking skills. Techniques such as problem situations, case studies, debates and comparative analysis can be used effectively to stimulate thinking.

The implementation of these mechanisms in the educational process helps strengthen students' independent thinking and contributes to their formation as competitive professionals in modern society.

Using interactive methods in the classroom:

Organization of work with historical documents and sources.

Encouraging teachers to reflect on historical experiences.

REFERENCES

1. Abu Nasr Forobiy- Fozil odamlar shahri – Inson tafakkurini rivojlantirish va bilimga erishish usullari haqida.
2. Ibn Sino. Donishnoma – Mantiq va bilimlarni o‘zlashtirish usullari haqida.
3. Ibn Khaldun. Introduction - Theoretical Foundations of Education and Social Development.
4. Yusuf Khas Hajib. Qutadg'u Bilig - A work on educational and intellectual upbringing. Modern pedagogical resources:
5. Vygotsky, L.S. Thinking and speech - Children's thinking process and teaching methods.
6. Dewey, J. How we think - About critical thinking and teaching methodology.
7. Piaget, J. Psychology of intelligence - About the formation of the thinking process.